

ORGANIZATION OF MONITORING OF THE TECHNICAL CONDITION OF HIGHVOLTAGE CABLE LINES.

Mustafayeva Gulnora.

Student of the Department of Electric Power Navoi State Mining and Technological University.

Turniyozov Zuxriddin.

Master of the Department of Electric Power Navoi State Mining and Technological University.

Hamidov Eldor.

Master of the Department of Electric Power Navoi State Mining and Technological University.

Annotation. A cheaper control option is the use of systems for periodic monitoring of the condition of cable lines, in which parameters are also measured on a working line in the “on-line” mode, but not continuously, but at certain time intervals. Therefore, such monitoring is called periodic. When conducting periodic monitoring, the condition must be met that the time interval between measurements should be at least two to three times less than the standard time for the development of a defect, from the moment it occurs to reaching a critical level. Only in this case is the possibility of skipping rapidly developing dangerous defects reduced to a minimum.

Key words: high voltage cable lines, crosslinked polyethylene, continuous monitoring, periodical, critical level.

To ensure efficient and trouble-free operation of high-voltage cable lines, the following five diagnostic methods and methods are preferable, the use of which is possible and justified in systems for continuous and periodic monitoring of the technical condition of cable lines. Distributed temperature monitoring of a high-voltage cable line, which allows you to monitor the longitudinal temperature profile of the cable line with a resolution of up to one meter. Such detailed information

enables maintenance personnel to control the operating conditions of the entire cable line, its operating temperature, and also to identify defective areas of the line with elevated temperatures.

Control of the presence of defects in the insulation of the end and connecting sleeves by partial discharges. More than half (according to some sources, up to 80%) of all cases of defects in high-voltage cable lines occur precisely in these elements of cable lines. Typically, the occurrence of these defects is due to insufficient quality work of the personnel when performing work during the installation of couplings. Defects in the installation of couplings appear either immediately when the line is put into operation, or after a certain period of operation, and are always accompanied by the appearance of partial discharges in the insulation (up to 95% of cases of defects). Much less often, defects in couplings are accompanied by an increase in the temperature of the coupling (on average, in 20–30% of cases). Therefore, the use of partial discharge control methods for monitoring the condition of couplings is most justified.

Diagnosis of the presence of defects in the insulation of the high-voltage cable itself. Defects in the cable are much less common than defects in couplings. The appearance of defects is preceded by either damage to the cable sheath, or leaky installation of the coupling, leading to the penetration of moisture into the cable insulation. It is moisture that most often causes damage to the main insulation of high-voltage cables; manufacturing defects in the cable insulation, although they occur in practice, are very rare.

Determination of the type and degree of development of a defect in the cable line, both in the couplings and in the cable itself. The availability of information about the type of the defect and the degree of its development has a great influence on the strategy for managing the operation of a cable line with identified defects. Knowledge of this information enables personnel to correctly assess the time of residual operation of the cable line, plan in advance the time and the optimal amount of necessary repair actions. The most accurate localization of the defect in the cable

line. These three methods are physically independent of each other, but when used together, they give the highest diagnostic efficiency:

II. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION.

A big problem in organizing monitoring of capacitive leakage currents is that in the screens of cable lines, in addition to informative leakage currents, induced currents of industrial frequency flow. The magnitude of these currents is determined by the current load of the line, the features of the mutual laying of phase cables relative to each other, and the presence of screen superposition points. To eliminate the influence of these currents, it is necessary to carry out comparative measurements only in the idle mode of the line, or use a compensated balanced circuit for monitoring three-phase currents in the screens of the phases of the controlled cable line. In this circuit, the induced phase currents cancel each other out. [2,3]

To control partial discharges in cable lines of 110 kV and above, a monitoring system of the CDR brand (Cables Diagnostics Relay), manufactured by DIMRUS, is designed.

The widespread introduction of high-voltage cable lines with an operating voltage of 110 kV and above, which are critical elements of power supply systems, requires the use of operational systems for assessing the technical condition. This is due to the fact that the rate of development of defects in XLPE insulation is abnormally high - it can take weeks or even days from the moment a defect occurs to a cable failure. Therefore, standard off-line tests, usually carried out no more than once a year, are not able to detect dangerous defective conditions and really reduce the accident rate of cable lines. The most effective way to control the state of

insulation of high-voltage cable lines is diagnostics based on registration and analysis of partial discharges. This method has the maximum efficiency and sensitivity for diagnosing defects in XLPE insulation.

RFCT-7 brand sensors.

Sensors brand PD-Line.

III. CONCLUSION.

Possibility of registration of pulses of partial discharges in a very wide frequency range, from 100 kHz to 1.5 GHz. The use of such a frequency range is due to the fact that the PD pulses, moving along the line, decrease in amplitude and increase in duration. If a pulse occurs near the sensor, then its frequency will be high, equal to hundreds of MHz. The frequency of the "remote pulse" can be "only" hundreds of kHz. The longer the line, the more low-frequency PD pulses can be registered in it. Two modern methods of locating the place of occurrence of a defect in the

insulation of a cable line are built into the monitoring system of the CDR brand. One works independently based on the analysis of reflectograms of the distribution of partial discharge pulses in the line, and the second analyzes the difference in the time of arrival of the high-frequency pulse from the defect to the "ends" of the controlled cable line.

To implement such a unique set of functionality in the CDR system, specific technical solutions were used: Firstly, this is that the registration of partial discharge pulses in all six measuring channels of the CDR device is carried out completely synchronously. Only in this case is it possible to implement all of the above diagnostic algorithms. Secondly, if a monitoring system is created to control several cable lines, then it has to be created using several CDR brand devices. In this case, the task of synchronization of partial discharge measurements becomes global.

REFERENCES

1. Kudryakov A.G., Sazykin V.G., Silchenkov A.S. Preventive testing of cable lines (CL). AT Sat: Fundamental and applied sciences today - IV int. scientific and practical. conf. Research Center "Academic". 2014, pp. 125–131.
2. Sazykin V.G., Kudryakov A.G., Nikolaev A.M. Organization of technical diagnostics of power cables by non-destructive methods. In: Materials of the V int. scientific and practical. conf. 2014, pp. 118–120.
3. Lebedev G.M. Diagnostics of the insulation of cable lines 6-10 kV by the method of high-frequency reflectometry // *Electrical*. 2005. No. 5. S. 39–41.
4. Aksenov Yu.P., Lyapin A.G., Pevchev B.G. Application of reflectometry for cable diagnostics // *INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC JOURNAL "INNOVATIVE SCIENCE" №02-1/2017 ISSN 2410-6070 Electric stations*. 1997. No. 4. S. 62–68.
5. Kadomskaya K.P., Sakhno V.V. Method of impulse diagnostics of couplings and cable sheaths // *Electrical engineering*. 2000. No. 12. S. 12–17.